

**Professor Marie Lall,
Chair of Education and
South Asian Studies,
UCL Institute of
Education**

Publishing open access drives access, impact and profile

– Marie Lall

Publishing open access enables Marie Lall to disseminate research more widely and reach her target audience in the Global South.

Open access fosters global knowledge creation and dissemination. It makes research more accessible, equitable and impactful. So says Professor Marie Lall, Chair of Education and South Asian Studies at the UCL Institute of Education. Lall currently focuses on the role of education as a safe space for students who are forced migrants, due to conflict or climate change.

Education reforms in Myanmar

Lall says it was particularly important that her most recent book – Myanmar’s Education Reforms. A pathway to social justice? - was open access so that people in Myanmar could access it. That would not have been possible with traditional publishing. Lall chose UCL Press because it was open access and the publishing fees were waived.

She said:

“Myanmar has had a coup. Nobody can go to a bookshop, nor do they think to spend money on a book, but they will click on a link and read it.”

The Myanmar book had been downloaded 37,724 times in 173 countries by July 2024, with 2,793 of those downloads being in Myanmar. She says the physical version could not achieve anywhere near those kinds of numbers.

She added:

“I would never have imagined selling over 37,000 copies of my book.”

Producing books people will read

Lall says she writes books so that people read them, giving her research a bigger audience. If she publishes the traditional route, it limits the number of people who can and will access her work. And it would definitely preclude her target audience, the Global South, including people involved in policy work, from accessing her research. Lall’s work has policy impact, which would be so much harder to achieve if it wasn’t open access.

Policy makers in the Global South have limited access to academic content that is published traditionally, as they often don’t have access to libraries or subscriptions.

Involving the local community

The majority of Lall’s work is field work, using data provided by people in the local community. Most of those people would not be able to access the research they contributed to without open access. She explained:

“ Open access has made all the difference. These people cannot buy the book or get hold of it and there’s no way I could send them copies. Open access takes that problem away. When it’s published, you just send the link to the community leads and they can download it or pass it on. Knowledge should be accessible to everyone.

Lall thinks that when the local community knows the research will be freely available to them it builds trust and makes it easier for her to ask for participation.

Making sure research has impact

Not only does Lall think publishing open access is a morally and socially responsible thing to do, she says it has also benefitted her career. Her work is more widely read, boosting her profile.

Lall acts as a mentor to junior researchers. When they ask her for advice about how and where to publish, Lall always advocates for open access. She likes co-authoring with junior researchers on open access projects, thinking it is a great way to help raise their profile. She said:

“ When you start publishing, academics normally go to traditional publishers who charge £100 or more for a hardback and nobody buys it. It’s only available in certain libraries. I say to academics ‘Do yourself a long term favour - try to make your research read’.